

Energy Versus Internal Energy and a Lorentz Boost of an Ideal Gas Part II

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The Newtonian concept of work: $\int dx \cdot \text{Force}$ seems to be directional as is the concept of momentum. The first law of thermodynamics: $dE = dQ - dW$ where dQ is heat and $-dW$ work often treats work in terms of global parameters such as volume or spring constant, while heat is associated with an averaging of single particle energies.

In this note, we consider the possibility of identifying work in terms of directional information and heat in terms of non-directional information. This approach implies that the concept of center-of-mass momentum is directional and associated with work, not heat. A Lorentz boost is also associated with a direction, namely that of the velocity v and so is linked to work (not heat). Heat or thermal energy is like rest mass. This energy, as rest energy, may transform due to directional work, but parameters like pressure and temperature, we argue, are associated with heat and need to be considered in a non-directional environment, namely the rest frame. It is possible to have $T(x)$, where T is temperature, but this implies that one has a tiny box in which T is isotropic. Specifically, $1/T = dS/dE$ no work is often used to define temperature. If (no work) implies no directional information, then we argue that one essentially has a rest frame, i.e. P and T pertain to this frame.

As a result, we suggest that care must be taken when considering statements such as Pressure (Lorentz boost) = $\gamma(v)\gamma(v)$ Pressure (rest) and Temperature (Lorentz boost) = $\gamma(v) T_{\text{rest}}$ (1). If thermal energy is proportional to T (as in the case of an ideal gas in a rest frame), this may transform to $\gamma(v) T$ ($1.5nR$), but $T \rightarrow \gamma(v)T$ describes directional work and does not mean that the temperature really changes, we suggest.

Work and Direction

We suggest that the Newtonian concept of work: $\int \text{Force} \cdot dx$ is directional. Center-of-mass momentum is also directional and linked with work in the direction in question. In addition, Lorentz boosts are directional, in the direction of velocity.

Given that work creates energy, it is possible to have directional energy. Not all energy, however, is directional. If one considers a gas in a container which is absorbing photons from all directions, then energy may increase without any net work being done, i.e. any directional information.

We suggest that this notion of direction associated with work may be key to the first law of thermodynamics:

$$dE = dQ (\text{heat}) - dW (\text{work}) \quad ((1))$$

In general, work is associated with global parameters such as volume or spring constant, while heat is associated with averaging. We suggest that work is also associated with directional information, following Newton's definition.

The reason for belaboring the notion that work is associated with direction and heat (thermal) energy is not that a Lorentz boost is also associated with direction and so is linked with work.

If one has a certain amount of heat energy (thermal energy) in the rest frame, one may perform work on this heat energy just as one performs work on rest mass. The work done then is:

$g(v)$ heat energy where $g(v)=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ ((2))

We suggest, however, that parameters like pressure and temperature, which are used to characterize heat energy even when no work is done are isotropic in tiny volumes and do not carry directional information within the tiny volume. For example, if one has a gas in a container and heat is added with no work, there is no directional information and pressure and temperature increase. These are isotropic in tiny dx (one dimensional example) boxes in the system and not associated with any work direction.

Thus, we suggest that values for pressure and temperature should not really contain directional information, such as v in the case of a Lorentz boost. In order to guarantee no directional information, one is forced to go into the rest frame to compute pressure and temperature and leave the definition of these quantities to such a frame.

Specifically, $1/T = dS/dE$ work set to 0 ((3))

We argue that work set to 0 means no directional information. ((3)) is often used as the starting point for defining temperature. If this quantity cannot contain any directional information, then it should be computed in the rest frame (as this frame contains no directional information for a tiny box), which is often not done in the literature.

One may note that in the case of a potential $V(x)$, there is x information, but this is not the same as directional information. We suggest that directional information implies motion in a certain direction.

One may further note that compressing a gas at one end of its container involves directional work. The directional information of this work, however, may be lost if the work is converted to temperature energy and there is no center-of-mass momentum given. For example, for an ideal gas, $E = 1.5 nRT$. Using the first law with no heat added or lost, a directional work may increase T , but no directional information remains. This is equivalent to the addition of nondirectional work through the absorption of photons as energy does not depend on volume. Thus, the idea of $1/T = dS/dE$ no work being associated with the rest frame still applies.

Lorentz Boost

As an example, we consider the notion of Lorentz boosting an ideal gas. It has energy $E=1.5 nRT$ in the rest frame (nonrelativistic). This may be a good approximation for the rest frame which has no net momentum. This is like a rest mass and gives rise to a boosted momentum $g(v)Ev$ and energy $g(v)E$, but these are work related quantities and are directional (i.e. contain the directional information v). We suggest that T and P should not contain this v information and so should only be defined for the rest frame.

In the literature (1), one sees Lorentz boosts which take T or P in the rest frame with no directional information and transform them into $Tg(v)$ and $Pg(v)g(v)$ which contain directional

information. For example: PdV = energy (directional work) which should transform as $g(v)$ energy, and $dV \rightarrow dV/g(v)$ so $P \rightarrow g(v)g(v) P$.

We thus caution about the interpretation of such values. For example $E g(v)$ is the work energy of a given thermal energy $E = 1.5 nRT$ and so it appears as if $T' = g(v)T$, but this simply means that a certain amount of directional work has been done on the rest mass like thermal energy $E = 1.5nRT$. T is still evaluated as a rest frame quantity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that Newtonian work is directional as is momentum and the velocity in a Lorentz boost. We suggest, however, that the first law of thermodynamics splits energy changes into directional and non-directional ones, i.e. work and heat. Thus:

$1/T = dS/dE$ (work=0) ((4)) means that no directional work is done. To guarantee no directional information, one needs to go into a rest frame. (Note: no directional information applies to motion, not changes in x . For example, a potential in a gas brings in x related information, i.e. $V(x)$, but this is not directional information. A tiny box of gas at x has uniform T and P in all directions.

Changing center-of-mass momentum, as in the case of a Lorentz boost, however, implies directional work and so one should only use ((4)) when there is no directional energy change, i.e. in the rest frame. Thus, we argue that T (and P as well (pressure)) are quantities pertaining to the rest frame.

It is possible to write $T' = g(v)T$, which brings in directional information if one considers T proportional to energy and notes that $g(v)T$ means that directional work is being done. The temperature is still defined in the rest frame and remains T , we argue.

References

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